

HISTORY AND STUDY OF GENDER STUDIES

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Abstract. *This article will talk about how important the concept of gender, which is one of the current topical treatments, is to be promoted to the life of society and, in Uzbekistan, to ensure women's rights, to protect women from violence and oppression. The article covers the origins of the term gender, its use in social fields, and the differences between women and men. dedicated experience testing and data on the effectiveness of the results were cited. Together with the analysis of the literature dedicated to Gender problems, a list of different types of gender relations and their corresponding gender characteristics is presented. Gender relations arise in the process of joint life-activities of representatives of a particular sex, various forms of relations between subjects are presented.*

Keywords: *gender, polarization, violence, gender relations, social relations, gender representations, gender stereotypes, domination, freedom, dependence, feminism.*

Introduction. Uzbekistan today has a unique role in achieving gender equality of modern education and has adopted a number of programs, legislation related to further improving the educational process, including the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan's decree and resolutions on ensuring women's rights, in particular, gender equality and protection of women from violence and oppression, strengthening the status of women's entrepreneurship, Uzbekistan today has a unique role in achieving gender equality of modern education and has adopted a number of programs, legislation related to further improving the educational process, including the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan's decree and resolutions on ensuring women's rights, in particular, gender equality and protection of women from violence and oppression, strengthening the status of women's entrepreneurship.

Despite the rapid formation of the fields of psychology in recent years, there are many gaps in our social way of life. Among the questions studied, in our opinion, family leadership is important. Interest in this issue, as well as family leadership, in comparison with other topics, fall into the ranks of the most changing and thought-provoking topics over time. The 20th century has established itself as a century of revolutions, and with full right it can also be called, family and marital relations, the century of revolutions. From the beginning of the century, great social changes began, which also did not take their toll on marriage and family. First of all, this is due to the mass inclusion of women in production and the fact that a woman leaves the narrow Family world and joins active labor and social life. The woman's economic independence undermined the man's traditional reputation as a breadwinner of the family. Social equality of the Sexes has also become equally important. Not only did this mean a woman's right to participate in labor, education, social security, socio-political life, but the issue of equality in the family was strengthened in the constitutions of progressive countries around the world. Until recently, a man was almost never considered in the social sciences from the point of view of gender, but the question lies when the gender differentiation of people began.

We know that Sigmund Freud is a scientist who was one of the founders of psychoanalysis. Psychoanalysis is the orientation of a person towards psychosexual, sexual inclinations and gender

relations. Freud focuses more on the opposite sex in the study of man. But this theory will not be the same for everyone, it is he who stands as a denier. Homi viewed Freud as wrong with his views on the subject. Freud approaches the points expressed differently. She says that women often put themselves in a low circle when compared to men. Because their life is based on a multilateral dependence on men. Historically, in contrast, women were viewed as secondary beings, not recognizing their rights as equal to men, and stereotypes hardened in society were instilled in women's minds as a result of yoni's constant emphasis on male superiority. Indeed, such gender stereotypes in society have caused social systems to make women come to such a low level. Also, Khomi argues that most women aspire to be men. The main reason for this, as Freud said, is not women's interest in the gram-opposite sex, but rather, the "reassessment" of masculinity in the eyes of women, that is, what a real man would be like. There are also some women who have qualities that are not found in current men. For example, it can be said that strength, courage, success, sexual freedom and the right to choose a partner. Khomi's ideas, which emphasize the importance of cultural and sexual roles, are a topic that is relevant today: a feminist worldview that attaches too much importance. Many researchers argue that even today the appropriate use of the scientist's ideas devoted to feminism is in white. This is helping to overcome gender stereotypes, major-minor conflicts, which are firmly entrenched in society.

Unfortunately, in recent times, the study of family problems has decreased significantly, and to date, it is not enough to conduct local research that allows you to comprehensively discuss the topic of change, formation and development of modern gender roles and values in a young family, taking into account various criteria and foundations. In addition, modern literature on family problems is steadily declining, in which gender issues are rarely addressed, and work on family and gender issues can be found today on a small number of the Internet and as separate articles. But in many of them, the conceptual problem is very relevant-often the concepts of marriage and family, gender and female studies are not distinguished, there is no unity in the definition of the concept of "gender" itself (obviously, this is due to the fact that in Russian the concept of "gender" does not have sufficient translation, and its original ambiguity and A special problem is the methodology of "female "and" male " studies. The disadvantage of many studies in this area is that they are not kneeling in the process of data collection and analysis.

The psychological climate of the family is a one-time and not at all unchanging thing. Each family member has a role in its creation, and it depends on their actions, and the psychological climate in the family becomes favorable or unfavorable. The real basis of a favorable family climate is marital relations. T. V. We fully agree with Bendas's opinion that marriage relations are influenced by several factors – these are: the type of marriage, the relationship of sexual relations with the hierarchical structure of society, whether a wife works or is engaged in domestic affairs; it is also important who is the leader in the family and also the formed culture of perceptions of gender roles in marriage.

The results obtained and their analysis. In modern literature devoted to Gender problems, gender relations are viewed as a type of social relationship, i.e., class and interethnic relations. It is in the literature on gender that gender relations are informed about the male and female gender, or groups of men or women organized by social individuals. However, because gender relations are a new stage, only a general description of this concept, which is presented in the scientific literature, has been proposed. Gender relations are various forms of relations between subjects,

arising in the process of joint life-activities of representatives of a particular sex. (Table 1 lists the different types of gender relations and their corresponding gender characteristics).

Gender relations and the ratio of gender trait types.

Table 1.

T/r	Gender communication levels	Gender communication visions	Gender communication visions
1	Macro level: "men's and women's groups - state" type of relationship	Social	Gender representations
2	Meso level: "group-group " (relationships of men and women groups) type relationships	Intergroup	Gender stereotypes
3	Micro level: "person-person" (interpersonal relationships of different sexes) type of relationship	Interpersonal	Gender relations
4	Intrapersonal level: relationship Group" I am individual-I am one representative of the gene"	Attitude	Tender ID

Gender relations are embedded in a broad social context and are manifested at different levels of society, these are:

- 1) at the level of society, socially organized relations between representatives of the state and gender groups;
- 2) relationship between different tender groups;
- 3) relationships between subjects of different sexes;
- 4) the attitude of a person to himself as a representative of a certain gender.

The use of the basic ideas of socio-constructionist orientation in the study of gender allows, first of all, to express redposition about the more active role of the socio-psychological characteristics of an individual or group as a subject of multilevel relations. Gender representations, stereotypes, attitudes, and identity of an individual or group not only function as derivatives and determinants of gender relationships, but they can also play the role of relativists by building and creating their own unique models and patterns of behavior. Secondly, it allows you to distinguish the specific foundations of the design of gender relations. Such grounds characteristic of all levels of Gender relations are: polarization, differentiation of positions of men and women as representatives of two gender groups, phenomena of inequality, domination, authority, subordination. Since these phenomena are focused on in the socio-constructivist paradigm, the roles and status and hierarchy of men and women, the subordination of their positions, can be considered as the main parameters for the analysis of tender relations.

Conclusion. Summing up the results of our research, we can see the "established" principles of Social Psychology in its depths, although the foundations of the scientific direction "psychology of gender relations" were created. Within the framework of scientific disciplines, the role of the psychology of gender relations was determined, and at the same time, sociology of gender, psychology of gender, gender studies defined the boundaries of the spread of gender problems in psychology, in addition, they made it possible to consider these areas of certain

theoretical and empirical potential scientific knowledge accumulated in them as the necessary conditions.

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